

Electrical transport properties and applications of some glassy semiconductor

Sanjib Bhattacharya

Department of Engineering Sciences and Humanities,

Siliguri Institute of Technology, Darjeeling-734009, West Bengal, India

Email id: sanib_ssp@yahoo.co.in

Abstract

Transition metal oxide (TMO) doped glassy materials generally exhibit semiconducting properties [1, 2]. They are particularly important due to their engrossing applications such as switching, electro–chromatic devices, optical and memory switching devices, etc. [3]. In glasses containing vanadium, the electrical conduction takes place by hopping of unpaired $3d^1$ electron between V^{4+} and V^{5+} states [1, 2]. Frequency and temperature dependent conductivity of TMO doped semiconducting glassy system [4] have been investigated in the wide range of frequency and temperature. The values of activation energy of ac conduction (E_{ac}) and free energy of polaron migration (E_H) [4] have been estimated. Dc conductivity of the as-prepared samples shows thermally activated non–linear nature, which has been interpreted with Vogel–Tamman–Fulcher (VTF) model [4]. Nanostructured glassy semiconductor [5] has been developed as gas sensor, which is strongly related to surface reactions, in terms of change in the concentration of adsorbed oxygen.

Keywords: Transition metal oxide, Ac conductivity, Gas sensor

References

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